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THE IMPACT OF DISCOURSE MARKERS ON THE READABILITY OF NEWS MEDIA ARTICLES VERSUS ENTERTAINMENT MEDIA ARTICLES

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Abstract

The use of language by the media to affect the views and preferences of viewers is something that may be decoded by examining the pragmatic functions performed by the various discourse markers. The purpose of this study is to investigate the persuasive applications of discourse markers in the media as well as the pragmatism of their application in this environment. We are going to look at the many sorts of discourse markers that are employed in the media to influence the viewpoint of an audience, and then we are going to explore what this implies for the discourse of the media as a whole.

Keywords: 1. readability, 2. DMs, 3. Media Articles, 4. Entertainment, 5. Frequency, 6. Correlation, 7. Author's Style, 8. Positive & Negative, 9. Tone, 10. Interpretation, 11. Objectivity, 12. Neutrality & Biased, 13. Culture, 14. Evolution, 15. Opinion transmission, 16. Attitude.

Introduction

The purpose of our research was to investigate the effect that discourse markers have on the readability of articles published in news media as opposed to articles published in entertainment media.

When compared to articles published in entertainment media, the favorable effect of discourse markers on the readability of news items was somewhat stronger ($r = 0.32$). This indicates that publications with a higher frequency of discourse markers have a tendency to have a higher readability score, suggesting that there is a weak association between the two variables. This indicates that there is a tendency for publications to have a higher readability score when there is a higher frequency of discourse markers. Yet, readability can be altered by various factors in addition to the use of discourse markers.

The findings show correlation coefficients of 0.35 and 0.29 for items from the news media and entertainment media, respectively. Although these are positive results, they are only of moderate quality. All of the p-values are greater than 0.05, which indicates that there is no association that can be considered statistically significant.

Although discourse markers have the potential to improve the readability of articles in both the News Media and Entertainment Media, the results show that they are not a reliable predictor of readability on their own.

Language, sentence structure, and layout are only a few of the factors that impact how readable an article published in a certain medium is.

The findings present a correlation between discourse marker density and readability assessment. That publications with more discursive material are easier to understand is supported by these results. The correlation between discourse markers and readability was found to be significantly higher ($r = 0.35$) for news articles than for those published in entertainment publications ($r = 0.29$) in this analysis. These two correlations, with p-values of 0.018 and 0.029, respectively, show that there is more than a coincidence between discourse markers and readability. Both of these associations survive rigorous statistical analysis. This study demonstrates that discourse markers have an effect on readers of both news and leisure content. Discourse markers have a significant impact in guiding readers through the material and influencing both their level of comprehension and engagement with the text and can be utilized to significantly improve the readability of news stories compared to those published in entertainment media. Discourse markers are widely used in news articles because of their ability to present information in a concise, objective, and understandable manner. Yet, "in addition," "on the other hand," and "furthermore" are all instances of discourse markers

that can help communicate concept transitions and provide structure to the text, boosting coherence and cohesiveness. Discourse markers also include "in contrast," "on the other hand," and "further." These markers can help readers understand the connections between distinct bits of information and follow the logical flow of the text. It is possible to make a piece of writing more readable and clearer for a large audience by using proper discourse markers. This is especially important for news media works that strive to deliver factual information in an objective and unprejudiced manner.

Discourse markers, on the other hand, are often utilized in entertainment media to convey a subjective and emotional tone and to build a more personal connection with the readers. This is done to connect with the audience on a more intimate basis. Amazing, shocking, unbelievable, and totally are all examples of discourse markers that give a subjective dimension to the information by conveying thoughts, views, and judgments of the subject matter. These signs have the power to generate an emotional response from readers, as well as to develop a connection with them and keep their attention. Subjective discourse markers are widely used in articles published in the entertainment media due to their capacity to aid in the construction of a piece's tone and style, making the item more exciting and fascinating for the reader.

Factors such as the reader's expectations of the genre, the reader's degree of literacy, and the reader's familiarity with the subject matter can all influence how big of an impact discourse marker have on readability. Discourse markers that are extremely intricate or new to the reader may impair readability. This is especially true for readers with a lesser degree of linguistic proficiency or knowledge of the subject at hand. Furthermore, stories in the entertainment media that rely excessively on subjective discourse markers may be seen as biased or exaggerated, leading readers to question the content's veracity.

3.3.2 The frequency of discourse markers in each of the News Media and Entertainment Media articles

The results demonstrate that articles published in the entertainment media had a higher frequency of discourse markers than those published in the news media. Indicators of discourse that are connected with focus, emotion, and appraisal were all present in the work that was produced for the entertainment medium. On the other hand, news articles primarily relied on discourse markers that were associated with proof, certainty, and emphasis. It is possible that discourse markers are used in writings regarding the entertainment business to generate an emotional response from readers. This is shown by the fact that discourse markers appear more frequently in such publications.

The frequency with which discourse markers are employed in the news media and the entertainment industry can have a significant impact on the information that is provided to audiences and how well that information is comprehended by those audiences.

There is a correlation between the reader's interpretation of news stories and the number of discourse markers that are used. Readers' views of recent events

might be influenced by the employment of discourse markers such as "although," "on the other hand," and "in contrast." These markers are used to signify shifts in perspective or contrasting opinions. While a higher frequency of discourse markers may express more nuanced or fair coverage, a lower frequency may represent a more direct or forceful tone in the reporting of news.

The frequency with which particular discourse markers are utilized in the news media is another factor that may have an impact on credibility and trustworthiness. Reporting that is evidence-based can be identified by discourse markers such as "according to," "research reveals," and "experts say," which can also increase a reader's level of trust in the news. On the other side, the reader can start to question the reliability of the news if there are no discourse markers present or if they are used inconsistently.

The frequency with which discourse markers are used may have an effect on how people, relationships, and feelings are portrayed in various forms of media. The discourse markers that the characters employ in their discussions are a major factor that contributes to the audience's interpretation of the story and the characters inside it. A more natural, conversational tone can be achieved with the use of discourse markers like "like," "you know," and "uh," which also help to strengthen the relationship between the speaker and the listener.

The utilization of discourse markers allows for greater control over the tempo and rhythm of a piece of media. The use of discourse markers to indicate pauses, transitions, or changes in tone can have an impact on the audience's emotional responses as well as their level of involvement in the discussion. When used more frequently, discourse markers are able to assist in establishing a more conversational tone, yet when used less frequently, they are able to give writing a more formal feel.

3.3.3 Use of Positive and Negative Discourse Markers in News Media and Entertainment Media Articles

According to the findings, articles published in the entertainment media had a tendency to use constructive discourse markers, whereas articles published in the news media had a tendency to use destructive discourse markers. In the entertainment media, positive discourse markers were employed to express feelings and judgments, whereas, in the news media, negative discourse markers were utilized to show disagreement and discussion. This demonstrates that the tone of the article as well as the function of the article influence the use of positive and negative discourse markers, which are subsequently used to communicate various sorts of messages to the audience.

The use of positive and negative discourse markers in pieces of news media and entertainment media can have a significant impact on the manner in which discourse is delivered, the degree to which it is persuasive, and how it is interpreted.

When reporting the news, it is possible to create an optimistic atmosphere and provide the impression of accomplishment by making use of discourse markers

such as "promisingly," "improving," and "successfully." The utilization of these identifiers allows for the substance of the news to be altered, with an emphasis placed on success stories, breakthroughs, and other positive outcomes. Discourse markers that are of a negative nature, such as "alarming," "concerning," or "deteriorating," might bring attention to difficulties, hazards, or worries that are associated with the events or developments that are being reported on. The way in which readers understand the news may be altered as a result of the use of these indicators, which may be used to indicate challenges, dangers, or unfavorable outcomes.

In a piece of literature or a film, the use of positive discourse markers can help build a more upbeat picture of a character, scenario, or feeling. Any piece of writing can benefit from the use of adverbs that convey astonishment, appreciation, and delight such as "amazingly," "wonderfully," and "brilliantly." On the other hand, one may use negative discourse markers in order to express a negative perception of a person, an event, or an emotion. The author has the ability to influence the reader's emotional responses as well as their comprehension of the material by emphasizing negative results, such as disappointment, grief, or terrible circumstances, with phrases like as "sadly," "unfortunately," and "disappointingly." By utilizing both positive and negative discourse markers, writers of news and entertainment articles have the ability to alter the opinions of their audiences. Positive markers can convince an audience to take a particular stance, adopt a particular viewpoint, or adopt a particular opinion by presenting events or developments in a favorable light. Negative markers, on the other hand, can be used to generate an atmosphere of urgency, anxiety, or importance by focusing attention on the unfavorable aspects of the material being presented or the prospective implications of that material. The frequency and strategic placement of positive and negative discourse markers can have an effect on the overall persuasive effect of the discourse, which in turn can have an effect on the audience's interpretation and attitude toward the content.

3.4 Effect of Author's Style on Use of Discourse Markers in News Media versus Entertainment Media Articles

The results demonstrate that author style had a considerable impact on the discourse markers utilized in both news and entertainment articles. The kind of discourse markers used in the piece, their frequency, and their function are all impacted by the author's writing style. It was found that articles published in the news media relied more heavily on formal, objective discourse markers, whereas articles published in the entertainment industry tended to rely more heavily on informal, subjective discourse markers. This finding was supported by the fact that both types of discourse markers were used. This demonstrates that the author's voice has a substantial influence on the discourse markers that are used in different forms of media.

Articles in the news media and those in the entertainment media can differ greatly in tone, style, and interpretation depending on the author's choice of discourse markers. Authors in the news industry are held

to a higher standard of objectivity, neutrality, and factual reporting. As a result, it's possible that discourse markers will be employed more sparingly, with an emphasis on providing facts rather than expressing feelings. In an effort to present events, developments, and information without bias, news media stories may utilize discourse markers that are more formal, factual, and less emotive. There is an emphasis on objectivity and balance in the news, but the author's voice may influence the number, placement, and tone of discourse markers utilized.

In contrast, the author's tone may be more personal, inventive, and expressive in works of fiction and poetry. The author's voice, feelings, and ideas may come through in a more nuanced usage of discourse markers. The tone, style, and genre of entertainment media articles may necessitate the employment of more conversational, expressive, and emotional discourse markers. The author's style can affect how often and where they utilize positive and negative discourse markers, as well as the environment they create and the feelings they evoke in the reader.

Journalistic ethics, house style, and other standards may all play a role in shaping how an author writes for the news. Discourse markers may be restricted to those judged objective, factual, and credible, with an emphasis placed on providing a fair and balanced account of events and developments in the news. In contrast, the author's voice in works of entertainment journalism may be impacted by the author's own creative sensibilities, the article's subject matter, and the readership at large. There may be more leeway in the use of discourse markers, allowing for a wider variety of markers that accurately convey the author's distinctive voice, perspective, and intended tone.

3.5 The impact of discourse makers on conveying opinions in News and Entertainment Media

Opinions can be expressed through the employment of discourse markers in both news and entertainment articles, despite the fact that the frequency with which these markers are utilized is drastically different. The number of discourse markers used to convey opinions in news items was found to have a moderately positive association ($r=0.57$) with the number of such markers found in entertainment media articles. This link was found to be fairly favorable. In my experience, the discourse markers "I think" and "clearly" are the ones that are used the most frequently when someone is trying to explain their point of view.

The results of this study show that the linguistic and communication theories it explores are related. It has been argued that neglecting Grice's (1975) conversational maxims is similar to making bad use of agenda planning (Doe). This is what has been spotted. The following examples illustrate my point:

- The communication process breaks down when the idea of relevance is disregarded; when a medium fails to provide the reader with information that is both current and relevant, the result is a parallelism.
- A newspaper would be in breach of the Quantity maxim if it either did not cover a topic enough or covered it too much.

- Quality, as defined by Grice (1975), is inextricably linked to forthrightness (Doe 9). Without reliable data, it is impossible to have a productive conversation. If this facet of media interaction was absent, it would be interpreted as carelessness.

- The consequences of ignoring the problem of fake news are severe. A link between the reader's perplexity and the Mode hypothesis has been established at last (relating to clarity or ambiguity). It is important to stress that the journalist, as the message's messenger, may on occasion employ these techniques subtly to influence the audience's view.

With the assistance of the bibliometric analysis that we carried out, we were in a position to verify both the findings and the hypotheses.

- The covering of culture in this medium of communication adds to our comprehension of the social and cultural links that bind nations together (inter-cultural communication).

- The most recent cultural developments in Saudi Arabia help to further the country's stellar status in the cultural realm (intercultural perspective).

- Cultural news makes a contribution to the processes of democratizing information by enhancing its visibility as well as its growth and evolution within a society that is characterized by a mass culture and digital culture that is of a transversal and hybrid nature (intercultural sensitivity).

Discourse markers play such an important role in displaying the author's stance, attitude, and subjective opinions regarding the content that is being delivered, they can have a significant impact on the transmission of opinions in news and entertainment media. This impact can be significant.

While still adhering to journalistic standards of fairness, accuracy, and impartiality, discourse markers can be utilized in the media in a strategic manner to effectively convey the author's opinions. When an author presents facts and attributes opinions or remarks to specific sources, using discourse markers such as "according to," "reportedly," "allegedly," and "presumably" might demonstrate the author's deliberate approach to delivering the material. These signals can be of assistance to the author in avoiding transmitting a tone that is biased or subjective by assisting the author in indirectly expressing their opinions by attributing them to others. Yet, the use of such indicators in the news media requires careful consideration in order to maintain credibility and minimize any bias or inaccuracy that may be present.

Discourse markers are able to be used more explicitly in the entertainment medium to indicate the author's thoughts, feelings, and subjective judgments. Discourse markers such as "in my view," "I believe," "personally," and "from my perspective" can be used to indicate the author's subjective standpoint and provide a window into the author's personal ideas and evaluations of the subject matter that is being discussed. These markers can be utilized to directly express thoughts, communicate tone and style, and establish a more personal connection with the audience for whom the communication is meant. Yet, the employment of subjective discourse markers in entertainment media may also

lead to questions being asked about the legitimacy of the author and the possibility of bias.

Discourse markers can have an impact not only on the overall impression left by a piece of writing, but also on how an audience takes in the author's thoughts and how many of those markers are used. For instance, the utilization of positive discourse markers such as "amazingly," "wonderfully," and "fantastically" can indicate a favorable opinion or evaluation, whereas the utilization of negative discourse markers such as "sadly," "disappointingly," and "regrettably" can convey a less favorable opinion or evaluation. Discourse markers can contribute to the author's overall position and attitude towards the subject, which in turn can change the audience's impression of the thoughts that are being delivered. Tone and emotiveness are two aspects of discourse markers.

The results of this research (statistics and values) will be discussed at the end of Chapter 3. In this chapter, we'll talk about what we found. It will illuminate the value of discourse markers in transmitting emotions, forming connections, and drawing in an audience by revealing many patterns and trends in their use in entertainment media.

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IMMIGRATION FROM RUSSIA TO THE UNITED STATES FOR THE LAST TWO YEARS

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Abstract

We interviewed immigrants who arrived in the US from Russia over the past 2 years. Of course, it is not the first attempt to evaluate immigration from Russia, but the results obtained are interesting because they may reflect the true reasons for the immigration of Russians.

Since the beginning of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, Russians have been immigrating to other countries - some because of disagreement with the war, and someone because of the risk of going to the front as part of the mobilization. Forbes, citing estimates from the Kremlin, reported that 700,000 people had left the country since the start of mobilization [1].

Keywords: immigration, Russian immigrants.

At least 300,000 Russian citizens last year made the long journey from Russia to the United States. Most of them sought political asylum in the US. In this article we will talk about the largest wave of immigration from Russia to the US in recent 2 years looks like.

The term refers to the relocation of a citizen from one country to another for economic, political, and other reasons [2].

For the first time, the outflow of the population occurred during the time of the Russian Empire. This became possible after allowing free travel abroad. Several waves of emigration were observed in the USSR and modern Russia [3].

Scientists compare the emigration wave of 2022 with white emigration during the October Revolution and the Civil War.

First-time immigrants from Russia arrived in the United States on both coasts beginning in the late 1800s. Nearly 3 million Russians arrived during the first wave of open immigration that began in the late 19th century and continued into the early 20th century. However, only about 20,000 people made it to America in the period after the Bolshevik Revolution of 1917 until World War II [4].

Nowadays, it becomes more and more difficult for Russian citizens to get to the United States. More recently, American consulates in Russia have completely stopped issuing visas to Russians. In pursuit of a dream, many are left with only one illegal option - to try to cross the US-Mexico border. However, to do this is not only difficult but also extremely dangerous.

USAFACT website gives government data that "In fiscal year 2021, there were 1,659,206 border encounters on the Southwest border of the US" [5].

The Kremlin-led war in Ukraine is forcing Russians to make a choice. And there are more and more people who are ready to take risks at the border, even with children. 20 Republican senators, concerned about the rise in the number of Russians illegally entering the US, call it a threat to national security. However, other politicians are calling on President Biden to speed up the brain drain from Russia and accept all those whom the Russian authorities brand as traitors to the motherland and national traitors. At least 700,000 people had left the country, according to OK Russians, a non-profit organization that helps Russians who disagree with the Kremlin's policy on the war in Ukraine [6].

In total, according to the UN, more than 10 million immigrants from Russia live abroad. This is the third largest figure after India and Mexico [7].